

Charge Transfer in Electronically Excited State[†]

SADHAN BASU

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

IN 1963 Leonhardt and Weller¹ observed that the fluorescent emission from pyrene in non-polar solvent is quenched by addition of dimethylaniline and simultaneously a diffuse structureless band appears in the longer wave length side of the characteristic emission spectra of pyrene. The absorption spectra of pyrene or dimethylaniline is not affected anyway in the mixture of the two substances, so there is no ground state association of the two substances and the new emission was associated with the association of excited hydrocarbon with amine in its ground state. In 1966 Mataga, Okada and Ezumi² brought forward further evidence of such association with other hydrocarbon-amine systems. These authors further observed that the intensity of the long wave emission was strongly dependent on the viscosity of the solvent. So, they assumed a diffusion controlled complex formation in solvents of low polarity according to

Because it has been found that the complex maximum emission frequencies observed in heptane and other non-polar solvents are directly related to the difference of polarographic oxidation reduction

potentials measured in polar solvents, like acetonitrile.

$$\nu = E(D/D^+) - E(A^-/A) - \Delta$$

where Δ is ion-pair stabilisation energy. Basu³ has proposed following energy level scheme for the new emission which is termed exciplex emission and the excited state complexes are termed exciplexes.

An approximate calculation may be made with anthracene-dimethylamine system. E_1 , the highest filled MO energy of anthracene is 7.56 eV and that of non-bonding electron at nitrogen atom in DMA is 8.23 eV as obtained from electron impact study. $h\nu$ for 365 nm band of anthracene is 3.29. This places the value of E_2 , the energy of the first empty MO of anthracene at 10.85. The exciplex emission energy is given by $E_2 - E_3 = 10.85 - 8.23 = 2.62$ eV, i.e. 473 nm. The experimental value of exciplex emission for anthracene-DMA system appears at 478 nm (Figs. 1 and 2). The agreement appears

Fig. 1. Pyrene-DMA systems. Pyrene 10^{-4} M. (1) DMA (0), (2) DMA (0.1 M), (3) DMA (0.2 M) and (4) DMA (0.3 M).

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Fig. 2. Pyrene (10⁻⁴ M) + dimethyl aniline (0.1 M). (1) heptane, (2) butyl acetate, (3) ethyl acetate and (4) methyl acetate.

Fig. 3. Anthracene (10⁻⁴ M) + DMA (0.1 M) in (1) heptane, (2) butyl acetate, (3) ethyl acetate and (4) methyl acetate.

to be excellent. It is evident that the exciplexes will be strongly polar, so according to Onsager's theory of liquid dielectrics the energy of the solute dipole will be different in medium of different dielectric constants such that the energy change compared to vacuum ΔE is given as⁴

$$\Delta E = \frac{\mu^2}{a^3} \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} - \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} = h \Delta \nu$$

which will show up in the position of emission frequencies in medium of different dielectric constant, *i.e.* as the dielectric constant is increased the emission frequency will show red shift. If the emission frequency in heptane be taken as ν_0 , then for any other solvent of higher dielectric constant,

$h(\nu - \nu_0)$ will be a linear function of $\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} - \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2}$

(Fig. 4). The slope of the curve will be determined by μ , the dipole moment of the exciplex, *i.e.* with the extent of charge transfer. The slope is given by μ^2/a^3 , where μ is the dipole moment of the exciplex and a is the radius of a spherical cavity in which the solute dipole finds itself. The radius of the cavity was calculated from the molar volume of the solute and came out to be between 4.5Å – 5Å for various systems studied. For a completely charge transferred state with the constituents at a distance of 4.5Å, the dipole moment calculated comes out to be 15.1D. Comparing this with the experimentally estimated dipole moment of the exciplexes it was estimated for dimethylbenzanthracene, methylcholanthrene, chrysene, benzpyrene, coronene and perylene as acceptor and dimethyl-aniline as donor, that the charge transfer was as

Fig. 4. Reaction field shift of emission spectra.

high as 80% in some cases and the lowest value was 60%.

Since exciplex emission appears with hydrocarbons and both aromatic and aliphatic tritertiary

amines, it is summarised that it is the non-bonding electron at the nitrogen atom which is transferred in the excited state charge transfer interactions.

It is an well established fact that the non-bonding electrons of heteroatom of organic compound are considerably stabilised by hydrogen bonding in hydroxylic solvents. It is expected, therefore, that more energy will be needed to transfer electron from amine to hydrocarbon in hydroxylic solvents⁵ than in hydrocarbon solvents. Consequently, the exciplex emission will show blue shift in alcoholic solvents compared to hydrocarbons. Unfortunately, all the alcohols are highly polar with large dielectric constant, consequently the red shift associated with reaction field stabilisation will be superimposed on the blue shift due to hydrogen bonding. If we could select two solvents having the same dielectric constant but only one of which can enter into hydrogen bond formation, then the blue shift effect of the hydroxylic solvent may be demonstrated. The dielectric constant of acetone is 20.7 and that of n-propanol is 20.1. Hence, the reaction field stabilisation will be about the same in both cases and exciplex emission will appear at about the same position in both cases in case hydrogen bonding stabilisation is absent. It has, however, been observed that the exciplex emission in n-propanol appears at a much lower wave length than acetone. It appears, therefore, the blue shift effect due to hydrogen bonding is in fact present in these systems (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Pyrene-DMA. (1) heptane, (2) benzene, (3) xylene, (4) mesitylene and (5) dioxan.

From what has been said before it is obvious that solvents for which

$$\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} - \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} = 0$$

i.e. for which $\epsilon = n^2$ the exciplex emission should appear at the same position as that in n-heptane. From Fig. 5 it may be observed that the exciplex emission is considerably red shifted in benzene, *p*-xylene and mesitylene, for which relation $\epsilon = n^2$ holds. As the benzene concentration is increased the exciplex emission is increased with respect to heptane⁶. This effect of aromatic solvents has been observed with all aromatic hydrocarbon-amine systems (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Pyrene-DMA. (A) acetone, (P) propanol, (B) butanol, (+B) tertiary butanol.

The exciplex emission spectrum from pyrene-dimethylaniline system in heptane containing different amounts of benzene is shown in Fig. 7. The intensity of exciplex emission increases with increasing benzene concentration and there is an isobestic point at 430 nm. This appears to indicate that there is only one new species with a maximum at 480 nm. Because of this finding the fluorescence transformation process may be attributed to a reaction of the following type which takes place during the life-time of the exciplex.

Fig. 7. Pyrene ($10^{-4} M$) + DMA (0.1 M) in heptane. Benzene (1) 2.8 M, (2) 4.2 M, (3) 5.6 M.

where $[D^*]$ and $[A]$ stand for exciplex and benzene concentrations, respectively. From the above scheme the following simple relation can be derived for the relative fluorescence intensity, f of the solution in which the concentration of benzene is A , f_0 being the intensity in pure heptane.

$$\frac{1-f_0/f}{[A]} = -K + \alpha K \frac{f_0}{f}, \text{ where } K = \frac{k'_r}{k'_r + k'_q} / \frac{k_r}{k_r + k_q}$$

From the linear plot of $\frac{1-f/f_0}{A}$ vs f_0/f , the equi-

librium constant for benzene exciplex formation may be obtained. The exciplex-aromatics complex appears to be similar to triple exciplex which has

been reported by Beens and Weller⁷ between naphthalendicyanobenzene exciplex with naphthalene. Beens and Weller proposed that in triple exciplex, the aromatic molecule acts as donor and exciplex as acceptor. The ionisation energies of benzene, *p*-xylene and mesitylene are respectively, 9.245, 8.445 and 8.400 eV. In charge transfer absorption process lowering of ionisation energy of the donor shifts the absorption band to longer wave length. Reverse appears to be the case for the emission process. Retaining Beens and Weller's model for triple exciplex the present observation may be explained by the following energy level scheme⁶.

It may be observed from the above scheme that as the ionisation energy of the aromatics is reduced, the triple exciplex emission frequency is increased, i.e. the observed blue shift with lowering of ionisation energy of the aromatic molecule.

Exciplexes have been postulated as intermediates and liable precursors to the products in various organic photochemical reactions. Effect of solvents on the exciplexes is of prime importance to the organic photochemistry in their selection of suitable solvent for photochemical reactions.

References

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